

Table 2: Results of code coverage by KLEE [6], *symsize* [61], and *SymLoc* in terms of instruction coverage, branch coverage, and line coverage (the percentage of the covered number of coverage / the total number of coverage)

Benchmark	Strategy	Instructions SymLoc	Instruction Coverage (%)			Branch Coverage (%)			Line Coverage (src) (%)			Line Coverage (src+lib) (%)		
			KLEE	<i>symsize</i>	SymLoc	KLEE	<i>symsize</i>	SymLoc	KLEE	<i>symsize</i>	SymLoc	KLEE	<i>symsize</i>	SymLoc
basename	BFS	290274771	42.39	42.24	42.39	29.17	29.02	29.17	97.60	97.60	97.60	42.20	38.90	38.90
	DFS	381999352	42.39	31.92	42.12	29.17	22.47	29.01	97.60	95.20	97.60	38.90	19.90	38.90
	Default	338203118	42.39	42.24	42.39	29.17	29.02	29.17	97.60	97.60	97.60	38.90	38.90	38.90
chroot	BFS	31873974	45.10	46.22	45.91	33.24	33.75	33.93	45.30	58.00	45.30	30.90	32.40	30.90
	DFS	740376347	45.48	48.72	45.48	33.73	36.74	33.73	32.60	49.70	32.60	31.20	34.10	31.20
	Default	90883760	47.54	47.39	49.81	35.16	35.21	37.74	62.40	64.60	68.50	36.00	35.20	39.20
date	BFS	13473597	29.43	40.38	29.49	17.66	26.41	17.74	34.00	54.50	34.00	23.80	35.80	23.80
	DFS	298647552	39.13	21.56	38.30	27.15	12.51	26.15	39.00	30.50	38.50	39.00	12.70	37.20
	Default	74682298	51.81	49.07	52.13	39.04	35.45	39.43	91.50	90.00	90.00	54.00	52.10	54.50
dd	BFS	158669129	50.72	44.62	52.27	35.96	29.42	36.77	45.30	36.10	44.90	39.60	32.90	39.40
	DFS	316674689	32.48	29.68	32.51	19.41	17.33	19.44	10.90	10.00	10.90	22.10	16.70	22.20
	Default	54775677	50.85	49.07	51.98	36.11	33.79	36.48	46.50	42.10	45.20	41.10	38.00	39.70
dircolors	BFS	104042126	49.93	49.49	49.17	35.39	34.92	35.60	80.30	69.00	86.90	44.80	42.40	46.40
	DFS	580284640	32.01	43.16	32.30	19.46	27.47	19.75	15.00	62.90	15.00	20.40	37.70	20.40
	Default	123130065	51.19	51.59	49.82	37.13	37.06	35.81	95.30	92.00	87.30	50.00	50.80	48.40
factor	BFS	311217326	39.03	33.86	40.06	26.84	22.76	27.93	27.20	22.00	27.20	24.00	21.30	24.70
	DFS	560207469	29.49	29.50	29.49	19.82	19.83	19.82	22.70	22.70	22.70	18.00	18.00	18.00
	Default	66661118	40.59	40.50	42.77	28.57	28.43	30.63	27.20	27.20	27.20	24.80	24.80	24.70
head	BFS	320822051	47.13	44.08	49.07	34.58	31.44	35.96	40.80	20.50	51.20	37.70	17.60	41.70
	DFS	622213575	36.55	40.09	36.30	25.57	28.78	25.30	20.30	30.50	19.60	23.90	29.00	23.70
	Default	208397508	50.87	49.71	49.78	37.60	36.80	36.55	60.60	56.30	68.20	52.40	45.30	50.30
ln	BFS	402041211	37.80	36.42	37.95	27.47	24.93	27.80	40.70	28.60	47.00	26.00	19.70	31.40
	DFS	653742940	31.27	32.04	31.50	21.11	21.51	21.55	21.80	21.30	21.80	13.90	17.30	13.90
	Default	310644698	42.82	43.24	39.97	31.65	32.05	29.91	63.20	74.30	79.80	36.80	37.80	40.30
od	BFS	387357494	39.84	35.06	39.76	28.43	23.85	28.39	45.20	21.10	40.90	42.10	23.20	40.20
	DFS	722247860	39.86	39.24	40.05	28.08	27.64	28.43	40.00	25.80	40.00	43.10	35.50	43.10
	Default	289663093	40.94	40.65	41.14	29.40	28.94	29.75	12.60	44.30	47.10	44.70	43.50	46.20
pr	BFS	463038369	27.44	27.03	27.73	17.99	17.39	18.24	41.10	39.80	41.40	34.50	33.70	34.60
	DFS	657217993	27.46	28.91	27.46	18.24	19.69	18.27	42.00	36.30	42.00	34.60	33.40	34.60
	Default	252266410	29.57	29.28	29.61	20.19	19.75	20.31	6.20	46.90	47.20	38.10	37.30	37.30
rm	BFS	337961473	37.69	36.50	39.47	26.02	24.95	28.05	55.50	45.50	53.00	27.70	25.40	31.80
	DFS	590190349	31.67	32.05	32.27	20.62	20.93	21.71	34.40	34.40	34.40	23.60	23.60	23.60
	Default	203884059	43.75	42.63	44.00	31.72	30.42	32.33	36.60	71.20	71.50	36.40	35.60	34.80
seq	BFS	388496014	47.74	47.81	47.74	34.71	34.94	34.71	62.30	62.00	62.30	34.80	34.80	34.80
	DFS	275577451	34.83	43.10	34.84	23.57	29.77	23.57	25.80	34.00	25.80	29.20	32.10	29.20
	Default	44192759	54.55	52.29	54.77	41.28	38.89	41.67	46.10	69.00	81.80	49.50	44.00	51.10
stat	BFS	459049716	30.53	29.81	30.91	21.10	19.82	21.56	29.30	21.80	31.00	24.20	20.70	24.80
	DFS	629074851	25.42	29.98	25.42	16.66	20.62	16.69	28.90	35.30	28.90	26.30	33.70	26.30
	Default	516586958	30.67	30.85	31.22	21.30	21.39	21.88	35.50	27.90	35.00	35.70	24.40	26.20
sum	BFS	214732041	49.30	48.46	49.33	36.20	34.72	36.44	40.00	23.70	39.30	30.10	17.80	30.00
	DFS	418163517	42.68	49.39	42.71	30.00	36.28	30.29	23.00	39.50	23.00	25.40	31.20	25.40
	Default	238049819	49.30	49.39	49.33	36.20	36.33	36.44	40.00	39.30	39.30	30.20	29.80	30.10
tee	BFS	383815306	41.51	41.39	41.76	27.75	27.64	28.19	71.10	71.10	71.10	44.10	44.10	44.10
	DFS	712522531	41.09	40.97	41.34	27.22	27.11	27.65	71.10	71.10	71.10	44.10	44.10	44.10
	Default	488327792	41.51	41.39	41.76	27.75	27.64	28.19	64.90	71.10	71.10	40.10	44.20	44.10
m4	BFS	640835	7.84	7.96	8.76	4.58	4.66	5.18	12.50	12.60	10.70	9.50	9.50	8.50
	DFS	701552	10.39	10.43	8.78	6.18	6.23	5.21	15.40	15.40	10.70	11.10	11.10	8.50
	Default	696706	7.98	9.56	8.76	4.65	5.86	5.20	12.60	12.60	10.70	9.50	9.50	8.50
make	BFS	218638537	29.64	24.65	16.96	20.12	15.90	10.35	18.60	22.10	23.80	22.10	22.10	23.80
	DFS	8888771	30.15	24.65	30.94	20.54	15.90	20.82	30.30	22.10	23.90	22.10	22.10	23.90
	Default	204389346	36.11	24.65	20.00	25.10	15.90	12.44	21.60	22.10	23.80	22.10	22.10	23.80
Num. of Best	BFS	-	3	3	11	3	2	13	8	5	10	7	5	10
	DFS	-	2	10	5	2	9	6	10	10	9	8	11	9
	Default	-	2	5	11	4	2	12	8	4	11	9	5	7
	Subtotal	-	7	18	27	9	13	31	26	19	30	24	21	26

* The first column shows the name of benchmark programs. The different search strategies are in the second column (i.e., *BFS*, *DFS*, and *Default*). The third column records the number of total instructions in the program counted by *SymLoc*. The columns 4-15 are divided into four groups; each group represents a different coverage measurement, i.e., instruction coverage, branch coverage, line coverage (for src only), or line coverage (for src+lib). Except for the numbers in the last four rows, each coverage number is calculated as: $\frac{N_{covered}}{N_{total}} \times 100\%$, where the $N_{covered}$ represents the covered number of instructions/branches/lines and N_{total} corresponds to the total number of instructions/branches/lines. The last four rows count the numbers of the best coverage achieved by each approach under each search strategy.